

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 15%

The author used the following software: Microsoft® Word for Microsoft 365 MSO (Version 2408)**List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):**

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

TIPS TO EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This course pack (ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (Period 1), which also acted as the key resource document for this Response Paper (RP), was authored by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma and revised by the same authors in the same year. The main aim of this course pack is to equip students with the necessary skills for paper and report writing. It is broken down into eight chapters. However, this response paper selected 8 out of the eight chapters. The first chapter is academic essay writing, which guides readers on how to begin writing an academic essay, choosing a research topic, structuring the research paper, referencing, editing the essay, and handing in the essay. This is followed by Chapter 2, which gives guidelines on how to use punctuations like brackets, colons and semicolons, quotation marks, and ellipses, and Chapter 3, which explains the difference between American and British English and finishes by stating that at EUCLID, both are accepted though it is recommended to use American English. Next is Chapter 4, which details what to do to avoid plagiarism. Finally, Chapter 5 elaborates on the academic style guide and why one is necessary with Turabian's recommendation as the style for EUCLID.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Despite the fact that there are several types of essays, this chapter emphasizes the academic essay. It states that academic essays should be based on research and should seek to validate some hypothesis with evidence. Educational essays must follow some form of formal writing style with all sources of information properly referenced.

i) Starting the essay

EUCLID (2024, 7) explains the necessary steps that need to be followed when starting to write an essay. Starting early is emphasized. It allows a student or researcher to have enough time to read through the research topic, write out the essay, and make corrections. The second step is being clear about the research topic and understanding the task at hand. This goes hand in hand with drawing a plan that will indicate what happens under each section and the specific timelines.

ii) Research topic

EUCLID (2024, 8) states that this is the most important step in essay writing because it answers the research questions, provides necessary evidence, and informs essay writing. The paper goes further to mention that taking notes or highlighting relevant sections as one reads is key. This is because it makes it easier to retrieve them during essay writing.

My opinion regarding the research topic is that by the time one decides to undertake a PhD course, one should already have an idea of what they would wish to research i.e., the research topic, information gaps, and as much as possible, choose a topic that they have already engaged with. However, I agree with the fact that a lot of reading and noting down all key points and references as one reads on is important so that these are not lost.

iii) Writing the essay and organizing ideas.

Once sufficient research around the topic at hand has been done and answers to the research questions collected, the course pack (EUCLID 2024, 10) provides the next step in writing the essay. Organizing ideas is key as it guides the presentation of responses to the research questions in a meaningful and structured way. Having an essay structure showing the order in which discussions will be presented is also necessary.

EUCLID (2024,10) breaks essay writing into three sections i.e., Introduction, the body of the essay, and the conclusion section, as the most common structure used for academic essays and other reports. In my opinion, a section for recommendations should be added after conclusions to provide a possible way forward based on the conclusions given. The trend has been that conclusions and recommendations are grouped, which swallows up recommendations, yet these are the pointers that should inform e.g., policy change, changes in practice, decision-making at various levels, etc.

iv) Referencing the Essay

EUCLID (2024, 11) emphasizes the need for reference not only as a way to let readers know the source of information but also as a way to guard against plagiarism. It mentions that, at EUCLID, any form of referencing is acceptable.

v) Editing the Essay

EUCLID (2024, 11) highlights a very interesting approach to editing essays, which proposes keeping the essay aside for a couple of days and then returning to do the editing. This allows one to think fresh through the arguments and have a fresh perspective.

vi) Handing in the essay

Before handing in the essay, (EUCLID 2024,12) recommends checking the guidelines and requirements before doing so. These include structure, content, referencing, page limit, font size, etc.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The course paper begins by stating a general rule in using punctuation, including using as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the sentence's meaning. It goes into specifics and begins with an apostrophe detailing when and when not to use this. Next, the section explains round brackets which are used in place of a pair of dashes or commas around phrases that add extra information to a sentence, and emphasizes that punctuation should be after the closing bracket. Next are the bullet points, which should not be placed at the end of bullets. And that if the text inside the bullet point is a complete sentence in its own right, a semicolon should be added to the end of each point. For colons and semicolons, a colon should be used to introduce a subclause that follows logically from the text before it if it is not a new concept and depends logically on the preceding main clause. It should not be used if the two parts of a sentence are not logically connected. It should be used to link two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other, and each of which could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence. Semicolons on the other hand, should be used in place of commas in a complicated list or sentence if it will improve clarity, particularly if list items already include commas. Commas should be used to surround a non-defining clause i.e., one which adds descriptive information, but which can be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence. But it should not be used where defining information is used at the start of a sentence. The course paper explains that ellipses are used to show that some text is missing, usually from a quotation. Usually, there is no need to add square brackets around an ellipsis. However, an exclamation mark or a question mark can and should follow the ellipsis if required. Finally, under this section, the paper explains quotation marks and says that they should be used for direct speech or a quote, as well as double quotation marks for direct speech or a quote within that.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The chapter begins by stating that American English has grown significantly since World War II and that it is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (cf. British English) largely due to population increase, increase in wealth of the US economy, the magnitude of higher education in America, the magnitude of the publishing industry in America, the magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence in America, the appeal of American popular culture on language and habits and the international political and economic position of the US.

The chapter also highlights the difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE), and these include;

- a) Words with the same spelling have different pronunciations.
- b) Words having different spelling but the same pronunciation.
- c) Same words having different or multiple meanings.
- d) Differences in grammar, syntax, punctuation, and general usage.
- e) Same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation.
- f) Differences in usage with SBE 'Large Collective Nouns.
- g) Differences in usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjective.

5) PLAGIARISM

EUCLID (2024, 33) explains plagiarism in detail and how to avoid it through correct citation and paraphrasing. It defines plagiarism to mean using another writer's information and ideas without acknowledging the source. It goes further to provide examples of plagiarism, including copying and pasting from the internet, using visuals and statistics, and not acknowledging the source. EUCLID (2024, 34) has given another example of plagiarism: "having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor." I tend to differ with this, especially in cases where a consultant or a research student is officially engaged to carry out some research on another's behalf, and then the same is presented to the professor for assessment. It makes me question whether this still amounts to plagiarism. To avoid plagiarism, EUCLID (2024, 35) provides that the solution is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using. It continues to highlight two types of citations that are commonly used which are;

- a) The in-text citation refers to citing the source of information you are using within the actual text itself. This is done in parenthesis by indicating the author(s) who

wrote the passage and the page from which this material came. This kind of citation is commonly used to cite quotations and paraphrases.

- b) Listing all the works cited, which are usually listed at the end of the paper, provides details of the sources of information quoted within the paper.

6)WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

EUCLID (2024, 40) In this section, the paper highlights that EUCLID's recommended style is Turabian. EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are accepted. All these requirements are stipulated in EUCLID's style guide, which aims to ensure a consistent, uniform way of presenting a finished piece, especially in cases where many authors contribute to one piece. And avoid unnecessary debates around the style to be adopted.

The paper also states that the ability to follow a standard English writing style should be an innate quality for any writer. However, just to ensure there is no room for inconsistency, a style guide is necessary.

7)CONCLUSION

This course paper is an eye-opener for me. I wasn't aware that in writing an academic essay, simple aspects like punctuation, brackets, and where to put commas and quotation marks mattered. Referencing and using Zotero is also a new thing that I have learned by going through this paper and Period 1 as a whole. Plagiarism has been emphasized not only in academic writing but also in official report writing on the risk of falling victim. This document has aided me in understanding the various options available to avoid this. Overall, this course paper will serve as one of my key resource documents as I move on with my Ph.D. studies.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401DCoursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.